

ANALYSIS OF REGULATORY LEGAL DOCUMENTS ON THE PREVENTION OF CRIMES COMMITTED BY MINORS

Khushvaqto Utkir Temirovich

Independent Research Fellow of the Academy of the Ministry of
Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17492112>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 29th October 2025

Accepted: 30th October 2025

Online: 31st October 2025

KEYWORDS

juvenile delinquency, prevention, regulatory legal documents, Presidential decree, Cabinet of Ministers resolution, mahalla, child protection, violence, legal culture, digital system, "Smart mahalla," interdepartmental cooperation, social prevention, victimological analysis.

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the current system of regulatory legal documents in the field of crime prevention among minors in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The author has studied, from a scientific and practical perspective, the essence and content of the Presidential Decree No. PF-6196 of March 26, 2021, the Resolution No. PQ-1 of January 3, 2025, and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 440 of July 14, 2025, as well as the mechanisms for their implementation.

According to the analysis results, these documents serve as an important legal foundation for the systematic organization of preventive activities, creation of a safe environment at the mahalla level, protection of children from all forms of violence, and strengthening of interdepartmental cooperation. At the same time, several practical issues were identified - insufficient effectiveness of interdepartmental coordination, incomplete implementation of digital systems, high workload of prevention inspectors, and inadequate provision of psychological and pedagogical approaches.

To address these shortcomings, the article proposes several practical recommendations: integrating the preventive activities of mahalla law enforcement centers into the youth engagement system, creating a unified information and monitoring platform, fully implementing the "Smart mahalla" program in all regions, establishing the position of an authorized inspector for child protection against violence, and widely applying protective orders and correctional programs in cases of violence.

The author believes that if these measures are systematically implemented, the effectiveness of preventing juvenile delinquency, ensuring children's rights, and raising legal awareness and legal culture in society will significantly increase.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 No. UP-6196 marked a qualitatively new stage in the reorganization of the activities of internal affairs bodies based on modern requirements, ensuring public safety, and preventing offenses, including juvenile delinquency. This document introduced a system of neighborhood law enforcement agencies at the lower level of preventive activities, through which a systematic

approach was established, aimed at identifying and eliminating the causes of crime at the level of each family and individual[1].

The mechanism of continuous management and control on the basis of "republic - region - district - mahalla," defined in the Decree, is aimed at ensuring the coordinated implementation of preventive work at all levels. Also, the digitalization of the activities of prevention inspectors (the "Smart Mahalla" program), the establishment of online communication with the population, thereby contributes to increasing the effectiveness of work with minors.

However, the results of the analysis of the implementation of this decree show that some of its norms are not fully effective in practice. Firstly, the preventive activities of mahalla law enforcement agencies are not sufficiently integrated into the sphere of working with minors. Prevention inspectors mainly deal with general offenses, and a special pedagogical and psychological approach for minors is insufficiently provided.

Secondly, the system of interaction between regional internal affairs bodies, educational institutions, the healthcare system, and mahalla activists is formal, and a unified information base or coordinating platform for working with minors has not been fully implemented in practice.

Thirdly, the tasks assigned to prevention inspectors are excessive, and the time and resources for their separate and systematic work with juvenile delinquency are limited. Therefore, the practice of individual work with minors is often limited to administrative measures, and the educational approach is not implemented systematically.

Fourthly, the digital system envisaged by the decree ("Smart mahalla") has so far been launched only in some regions, and the possibilities of early detection of offenses related to youth and children through it have not been fully developed.

From this point of view, although this decree serves as an important regulatory framework in the field of juvenile delinquency prevention, the following measures are proposed to increase the effectiveness of its current implementation:

integration of juvenile prevention with the activities of mahalla law enforcement agencies;

Implementation of an integrated coordinating information system between internal affairs, educational, healthcare, and family institutions;

Strengthening the system of psychological and pedagogical qualification training of prevention inspectors for working with youth;

Full implementation of the "Smart Mahalla" program in all regions and its adaptation to the process of working with minors;

Establishing specific indicators and criteria for assessing the effectiveness of preventive work.

2) The content of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 3, 2025 No. PP-1 "On Measures to Create a Safe Environment and Further Increase the Effectiveness of the Early Prevention System of Offenses in Mahallas of the Republic in 2025") is based on the principles of social well-being and effectiveness, aimed at creating a safe environment in the mahalla and early prevention of offenses. However, in practice, the above-mentioned problems, such as the lack of integration of mechanisms, lack of resources,

incomplete functioning of digital systems, and insufficient coverage of special areas, limit the full achievement of the developed goals of the decision[2].

Suggestions:

a "Center for Coordination of Crime Prevention" shall be established at the district (city) level, in which representatives of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Ministry of Employment, the Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Public Education, the Ministry of Youth Policy, and the Ministry of Family Affairs shall operate on a permanent basis;

creation of the "Mahalla Security Fund" at the expense of the state budget and sponsorship funds, directing its funds to preventive measures, stimulating public control groups and updating information systems, as well as the introduction of legal and psychological training courses for mahalla activists, prevention inspectors and volunteers;

To effectively ensure the implementation of Resolution No. PP-1, it is necessary to strengthen system integration, material support, digital monitoring, and the activity of social institutions.

If these proposals are implemented, the effectiveness of creating a safe environment at the mahalla level and early prevention of offenses will increase significantly.

3) Protecting children from all forms of violence is a priority of state policy. However, practice shows that the existing legal and organizational mechanisms do not fully ensure the possibility of early detection and effective elimination of cases of violence against children. This is explained, first of all, by the insufficient interdepartmental coordination, the lack of a systematic approach to preventive work, and the weak exchange of information between responsible bodies.

The Regulation "On the Organization of the Activities of the System for Protecting Children from All Forms of Violence," approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 440 of July 14, 2025, serves as an important legal basis in this area. However, the analysis of practice shows the need for additional institutional and organizational measures for the effective implementation of the tasks provided for by this Regulation. In this regard, the following scientific and practical proposals can be put forward:

Firstly, in order to institutionally strengthen the system of protecting children from violence, it is necessary to clearly define the legal status and powers of the "Inson" social service centers at the legislative level, strengthen their material and technical base, and introduce the position of a specially authorized inspector for the protection of children's rights in each region. This, along with increasing the effectiveness of the system, ensures guaranteed protection of children's rights.

Secondly, in order to improve the mechanisms of information exchange and coordination, it is necessary to create a unified electronic database between the "Inson" centers, internal affairs bodies, healthcare, and educational institutions. Through this system, data on cases of violence can be monitored in real time and the child's risk level can be assessed.

Thirdly, it is necessary to expand psychological and social rehabilitation services. For this purpose, it is advisable to create special psychological support centers for children who have suffered from violence, as well as to introduce a system of regular professional development of social workers and pedagogical psychologists.

Fourthly, it is necessary to develop a mechanism for the effective implementation of protection orders and correction programs. A system of control with the participation of prevention inspectors, mahalla activists, and social workers should be established in relation to persons who have been issued a protection order, and the practice of mandatory psychological correction programs for persons who have committed violence should be expanded.

Fifthly, strengthening preventive activities and ensuring public participation are of great importance. By organizing regular preventive projects in schools and mahallas with the participation of children and parents, such as "Violence-Free Family," "Children's Rights Week," it is possible to form a culture of intolerance to violence.

Sixthly, it is necessary to establish a system of scientific analysis and monitoring. For this purpose, it is advisable to introduce a system for analyzing cases of violence against children, identifying causes and conditions, and publishing the results in the form of an annual national report. At the same time, universities and research centers should conduct scientific research based on victimological analysis.

Seventh, it is necessary to improve legislation. In particular, it is proposed to introduce additional norms to ensure the safety of children in the digital environment in the Law "On the Protection of Children from All Forms of Violence," as well as to strengthen administrative liability measures against persons who concealed or did not report cases of violence.

The system of proposals developed in this way serves to identify, eliminate, and effectively organize preventive measures against violence against children. As a result of the implementation of these proposals, an effective national mechanism based on the principles of human rights and social justice can be formed in the victimological prevention of offenses.

In conclusion, it is clear that increasing the effectiveness of the above-mentioned legislative acts and their correct application in practice, as well as the constant consistent implementation of efforts to raise legal awareness and legal culture in society, creating an atmosphere of intolerance towards harassment and violence, will lead to a decrease in violence.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 No. UP-6196. <https://lex.uz/docs/1297315>.
2. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 3, 2025 No. PP-1 "On Measures to Create a Safe Environment in Mahallas of the Republic and Further Enhance the Effectiveness of the System of Early Crime Prevention in 2025." <https://lex.uz/docs/1297315>.
3. Regulation on the Organization of the Activities of the System for Protecting Children from All Forms of Violence, approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 440 of July 14, 2025. <https://lex.uz/docs/1297315>